

ABDULLA KAHHAR – THE SPEAKER OF TRUTH

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Abstract. *In a time full of hardships and when people who think cleanly and speak the truth are decreasing, a person like Abdulla Qahhor spoke the truth like a free bird without fearing any problems, and in the current era, the truth is attention deficit is one of our biggest problems.*

Keywords: *Abdulla Qahhor, truthful, works of Abdulla Qahhor, truth, genres.*

INTRODUCTION

The writer Abdulla Qahhor, one of the greatest representatives of the great Uzbek literature, was born on September 17, 1907 in the village of Asht in the city of Kokand in a family of blacksmiths. If we look at the time when Abdulla Qahhor was born, those times correspond to the colonial times of our country and the times when the dignity of our people was crushed. Remembering these times, we can cite as an example what Uzbek poet Hamid Olimjon said: «I was born on a dark day, I was born and drowned at that moment» Abdulla Qahhor is the only surviving child in the family, despite the fact that many children were born before him, but for certain reasons they died. His childhood, like many people's, was difficult and deprived.

At this point, it should be noted that when he was only seven years old, the First World War, which shook the world, and later the Second World War began, and his lifestyle became more difficult, he moved to many cities and wandered. Were, of course, these periods did not fail to influence young Abdulla Qahhor's thinking, worldview, mentality, and character, and he revived these events with mastery and skill in his works. For example, we can cite the following: the novel «Sarob» and the short story «Tales from the Past». Abdulla Qahhor, playing the game «White poplar, blue poplar» in his youth, how much he wanted to be chosen, to run and break the hands of his friends, but instead of choosing him, he was chosen. He remembers being insulted as a «foreigner» with a sad, close heart, and we can see that it had a strong impact on his future and character. So, how much a person is influenced by the environment around him, his friends, and their words, we saw this in the case of Abdulla Qahhor, even if only a little, that's why every person should read his words a thousand times before saying something. It is better to listen and then speak. It is not for nothing that our ancestors said: «Think first, then speak»

MAIN PART

He proved the sharpness of his pen in «Kyzil Uzbekiston» newspaper, «Mushtum» magazines, which were famous in his time, and participated with the signatures of «Norin Shilpiq» and «Mavlano Kufur». Abdulla Qahhor is a master of words, he knew very well what to say where and in what situation, he was able to distinguish people very well and, of course, he paid a lot of attention to choosing students. At the same time, he attracted the attention of many literary shinavandas and gained fame due to his shortness of speech, seriousness, and his stories, works, and skill in using words. He did not limit himself to writing works, but also tried himself in the field of translation.

World-famous writers translated the works of Pushkin, Leo Tolstoy, Gogol and Chekhov in a skillful and understandable way. In turn, his works have been translated into Russian,

Ukrainian, Kazakh, Tajik, English, German, French, and Polish languages and have seen the world. It should be noted that the famous writer Chekhov, who is considered a great storyteller in Russian literature, was considered his mentor by Abdulla Qahhor, and Uzbek writers and readers called Abdulla Qahhor: «The Chekhov of the Uzbek people». This is a proof of his skillful penmanship. He created literature in the genres of stories, essays, short stories, and novels, but despite the small volume of these genres, the genre of stories has a special place in the minds of listeners. For example, if we remember the story «The Patient» that we all read, «Sotiboldi's wife fell ill. Sotiboldi taught the patient – it didn't work, he showed it to the doctor. The doctor took blood, the patient's eyes were closed, his head became dizzy, he read the prescription. Somehow a woman came and beat him with a willow stick, butchered a chicken and it bled. Of course, all this will be done with money. In such times, the thick is stretched, the thin is cut»¹, about the sad incident that happened to Sotiboldi, his servant who works in the house of Abdughaniboyini, who is considered the hero of the play, who trades in seeds, pods and kunjara, and his family, that is, his young wife. That he died early due to an unknown disease, and Sotiboldi was unable to do anything and was left alone with his daughter, who had just turned 4 years old. The person who reads this story will undoubtedly have questions like «Why did this happen, how was his wife sick, even if she had an incurable disease?», and no reader will be indifferent to this situation. So, what caused this? Is it their laziness, their gullibility, their hope for Sotiboldi's master, and his neglect of it, and his anger over money, if all this is greater than human life? Look, it's very interesting that so many questions arise over such a small work. Sotiboldi needed money to bury his wife, how desperate a person is at such times.

The reason for all this is the period of that terrible regime, the backwardness of people, and the lack of knowledge of the doctor. So, the patient is not actually Sotiboldi's wife, but the whole society is a patient – sick and in need of recovery. The fact that there are so many lessons and opinions that the reader can take into account in this short work is a proof of the skill of the writer. In his works, Abdulla Qahhor expressed the truth, pain, and life of the people truthfully, and despite the fact that he faced various dangers and difficulties during the Soviet regime, Abdulla Qahhor never stopped, on the contrary, he drew the right conclusions from them and created his work. Continued with a sharper pen. He always lived with the pain of the people, fought for the truths despite the obstacles, loneliness, and rejection until the end of his life. He refrained from evil, hypocrisy, and indolence, hated hypocrisy, begging, preferred to speak the truth regardless of any situation, and did not bring those who told lies close to him. Unfortunately, our brothers, who were jealous of some of the wealth that came out of our people during the Soviet period, made their value, spiritual wealth, traditions, and customs one with the earth, and it is very painful for our writer like Abdulla Qahhor. It is no exaggeration to say that it was a shock. As for today, unfortunately, we can clearly see the lack of attention of the current young generation to literature. They do not hesitate to lie for their own interests instead of caring for the nation and acting, it is difficult to imagine fighting for the truth, this is a very sad situation, it is wrong to say that everyone is the same, we have such young people that we are happy to see their love for books, efforts to improve our spirituality, economy, respect for our history, great figures, poets-creators.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Abdulla Qahhor is a great storyteller and master of words who spent his short life conscientiously and meaningfully, for the people, for the nation, for literature, and we,

¹ Abdulla Qahhor - "The Patient" story, 1936

the youth, should follow their example and draw the necessary conclusions, we need to apply these to our lives correctly, because we can be a salve for the heartaches of the nation through words and literature. As Abdulla Qahhor said: «Literature is stronger than an atom, but its power should not be spent on burning wood».

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